

Theoretical binding affinities and IR spectra of β -cyclodextrin to non-essential amino acids

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Abstract : AM1 method is used to study the structures and characters of the complexes formed by β -cyclodextrin (β -CD) and non-essential amino acids to obtain the binding energies. On the basis of the AM1 optimized geometries, the IR spectra of the complexes are computed using AM1 method. It is indicated that β -CD can form the supra-molecular complexes with the non-essential amino acids, leading to the decrease of the total energy for the complex. The binding energies of the complexes are affected by the relative position of the functional groups between the guests and the host, as well as the electron-donating abilities of the groups. Especially, β -CD shows the chiral binding affinity to the non-essential amino acids due to its chiral characteristics. β -CD can bind D-alanine best. The polar groups on the guest molecules are located near the small rim of β -CD, which effectively forms the hydrogen bonds. The changes of the IR absorptions are caused by the different amino acids. The stretching vibration frequencies of the O-H and N-H bonds on the guest molecules are reduced with the formation of the complexes.

Keywords : Binding affinities, amino acids, β -cyclodextrin.

Amino acids widely exist in animals and plants. Some amino acids must be absorbed from outside since they can not be synthesized in the body of the animals. They are known as the essential amino acids. Other amino acids, which can be synthesized in the process of hepatic deamination and transamination in the body, are the non-essential amino acids. They play an important role in the synthesis of the protein, the expression of the gene and the performance of enzyme function as well as the liquid control in the human body. Chankvetadze *et al.* have studied the separation of the chiral isomers, and measured the equilibrium constants of the chiral complexes formed by β -CD and modified β -CD with the pharmaceutical molecules and amino acids¹. The chiral resolution of the arginine, arginine derivatives and other chiral substances has been previously reported using various chiral selectors as chiral stationary phase or additives², such as cyclodextrins³, macrocyclic antibiotics⁴, micelles⁵ or crown ethers⁶. The combination of the enantioselectivities of L-valine diamide and permethylated β -cyclodextrin in the chiral stationary phase of gas chromatography are studied by Levkin *et al.*⁷. It is shown that the existence of β -cyclodextrin greatly improves the enantioseparation of

proline. Liu *et al.* have investigated the binding ability and assembly behavior of the complex formed by β -CD with dipyrindine. They indicate that the hydrogen bonds and π - π interactions are the crucial factors for the formation of these molecular aggregates⁸. It has been reported that the sign of the circular dichroism depends on the orientation of the phenol molecule with respect to the axis in the cyclodextrin cavity⁹. Neugebauer *et al.* have discovered that the interaction between the guest molecules and the chiral host leads to a distortion of the geometry for the host¹⁰. Cyclodextrin also plays the significant role in the photocyclodimerization reaction of 2-anthracenecarboxylic acid, which is ascribed to the combined effects of the less-symmetric cavity and the electrostatic interactions¹¹.

The complexes formed by β -CD with the non-essential amino acids are explored here by studying the interaction between the host and guest molecules, to simulate the molecular binding process in animals and plants. This investigation has the remarkable importance in medical science and bionics.

Calculation methods :

AM1 method has been justified as a successful method

in studying the structures and IR spectra of the supermolecular complexes and organic compounds¹²⁻¹⁵. The binding energy of the complex is defined as the total energy of the complex minus the energy of each guest molecule¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Complexes 1-11 are formed in the mole proportion of 1 : 1 by β -CD and the guest molecules D-cysteine, D-alanine, D-serine, D-aspartic, D-asparagine, L-cysteine, L-alanine, L-serine, L-aspartic, L-asparagine and glycine as shown in Fig. 1^ψ. Using the standard bond lengths as the initial input, the carbon chains or rings in the guest molecules are vertically inserted into the cavity along the middle axis from the large rim of β -CD in CHEM 3D. The -COOH group on the guest is situated near the small rim of the host. Full geometry optimization for the host, guests and complexes is performed with the AM1 method¹⁹, respectively, and the binding energies of the complexes are obtained. IR frequencies and intensities are calculated using the AM1 method in GAUSSIAN 03 program²⁰ based on the AM1 optimized geometries.

Fig. 1. The guest molecules studied.

Results and discussion

Optimized binding energy :

As the binding energies of complexes 1-11 in Table 1 are all negative, the complexes can be formed. The bigger absolute values of the binding energies lead to the higher

stabilities of the complexes. Liu has proved the error of the binding energies for the complexes similar to the above is about 0.0016 eV²¹. The formation of the hydrogen-bonded network and the suitability in space of the geometries between the host and guest molecules, shown in Fig. 2, result in the higher binding energies of complexes 2, 3, 9 and 10. Among them, the binding energy of complex 2 is the highest. Except for the mentioned causes above, the polar groups on guest 2 are located near the small rim of the host, and the dense electron cloud on the host overlaps with that of guest 2, producing the electron piling-up interaction and ion-dipole interaction. The binding energy of complex 4 is lower than the others, because the hydrogen bonds between the amino group on the guest and the host are less. Moreover, the carbon chain of guest 4 is so long that the hydroxyl groups are extended out of the host. Therefore there is less interaction between the host and guest 4. The binding energy of complex 4 is close to -0.1230 eV of the complex formed by α -CD and L-leucine²². Guest 9 completely enters the cavity of the host by twisting its carbon chain to form many hydrogen bonds, which stabilizes complex 9. The binding affinity of complex 10 is large since the amino group on guest 10 located near the small rim of the host is surrounded owing to the hydrogen-bonding network. At this situation, the guest molecule well matches with the host in space and charge. This was in agreement with the experiment that the hydrogen bonding is formed by the atoms H on α -CD and the atoms O on the guest, which locks the photo-driven motion of α -CD²³.

Table 1. The binding energies (ΔE) of complexes 1-11

Complexes	1	2	3	4	5	6
ΔE (eV)	-0.1628	-0.2749	-0.2465	-0.1372	-0.1976	-0.1893
Complexes	7	8	9	10	11	
ΔE (eV)	-0.1957	-0.1851	-0.2139	-0.2742	-0.1684	

β -CD also showed the chiral binding ability. Guests 3 and 8 are chiral enantiomers. The binding ability of the host to guest 3 is better than that to guest 8. Though there are 10 hydrogen bonds both in complex 3 and 8, all the atoms with great electronegativity on guest 3 are used to form the hydrogen bonds with the host. But the hydroxyl group on guest 8 situated near the large rim of the host is free, which has no contribution to the formation of complex 8. Consequently, the stability of the complex is affected by the relative position between the host and guest molecule, and the space suitability is the main factor in chiral binding process. β -CD has the chiral binding

^ψPersons interested in additional materials (Figs. 1 and 2) may contact the senior author.

Fig. 2. The optimized geometries and hydrogen-bonding meshwork of the complexes.

microenvironment formed by many chiral carbon atoms²¹. That's why β -CD can bind the chiral enantiomers.

Electronic structures at the ground state :

The LUMO-HOMO energy gaps of complexes 1-11 are shown in Fig. 3. There is a little difference among the energy gaps of these complexes except those of complexes 1 and 6. Each of them is lower than that of the host. Then the electrons in the complexes are easy to be excited by the energy outside, which leads the electronic transition. It is predicted that the first absorption peaks in the electronic spectra of the complexes are red-shifted compared with that of the host. This is because the interaction between the host and guest molecules alters the electronic character of the host. Its HOMO energy is enhanced, while its LUMO energy is reduced, then its

energy gap is depressed. Guests 1 and 6 are the chiral enantiomers. The atoms S on guests 1 and 6 have the large electron cloud, and the shape of the electron cloud is easily changed. This electron cloud can effectively overlap with the ringed electron cloud formed by the atoms O near the large rim of the host. Then the conjugated systems in complexes 1 and 6 are enlarged, leading to the less energy gaps. The energy gaps of the complexes formed by the chiral enantiomers are almost equivalent, indicating that the arrangement of the groups -OH and -NH₂ has little influence on the energy gap.

The Müliken charges of the guest molecules in complexes 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 9, 10 and 11 are -0.0044, -0.0011, -0.0028, -0.0033, -0.0025, -0.0038, -0.0014 and -0.0003, respectively. The atoms O and N on these guests own the strong electronegativities. They can form the hydrogen bonds with the host and attract the electrons from the host, which results in the negative charges on the guest molecules.

Other important variables :

The ionization potentials (IP), electron affinities (EA), absolute hardness (η), absolute electronegativity (X_s), and the enthalpies of formation (ΔH) of the complexes are shown in Table 2. The less value of IP and greater value of EA lead to the stronger reactive abilities of the complexes in the oxidation-reduction reaction. For instance, the values of IP and EA of complex 6 are all small, thus complex 6 are not ready to gain but lose the electron. It is resulted from the presence of the atom S

Fig. 3. The energy gaps of complexes 1-11.

Table 2. The other important variables

Complexes	1	2	3	4	5	6
IP (eV)	9.2530	10.0865	9.7135	10.4433	10.1156	9.4234
EA (eV)	-0.4702	-1.0188	-1.1372	-0.4934	-0.7734	-0.1747
η (eV)	4.8616	5.5527	5.4253	5.4683	5.4445	4.7990
X_s (eV)	4.3914	4.5339	4.2881	4.9750	4.6711	4.6243
ΔH (eV)	-0.1154	-0.2183				-0.1413
Complexes	7	8	9	10	11	
IP (eV)	10.3497	10.3312	10.4601	10.2922	10.3554	
EA (eV)	-0.7573	-0.7636	-0.4406	-0.7451	-0.7524	
η (eV)	5.5535	5.5474	5.4503	5.5186	5.5539	
X_s (eV)	4.7962	4.7838	5.0098	4.7736	4.8015	
ΔH (eV)	-0.1450	-0.1396	-0.1689	-0.2208	-0.1192	

with the great deformability of the electron cloud. η is used to measure the resistance of changing the number of the electrons. Its greater value leads to the higher stability of the complex. It can be seen that complexes 2, 7 and 11 are more stable, because the guest molecules in these complexes are so small that they can be contained inside the cavum of the host. The escaping tendency of the electrons can be measured by X_s . The value of X_s for complex 9 is the greatest among the studied complexes. Thus complex 9 is hard to be oxidized. The complexes formed by the chiral enantiomers, just as complexes 1 and 6, 2 and 7, possess the close values of IP and η . It is illuminated that their anti-oxidation abilities and thermodynamic stabilities are almost the same.

The standard enthalpy change of formation (ΔH) is listed in Table 2. The greater value of ΔH indicates the higher stability of the complexes. The standard enthalpy change of formation is defined in the same way as the binding energy. It can be found that the values ΔH of the complexes are all negative, so that the complexes can be formed thermodynamically. The changing regularity of ΔH in Table 2 is coincident with that of ΔE in Table 1.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of complexes 1 and 2 are demonstrated in Fig. 4. Some characteristic absorption peaks such as the peak at 580 cm^{-1} are not affected by the guest molecules with the formation of the complexes, which can be considered as the quantitative peak of β -CD¹¹. The IR spectra of the complexes are similar to the simple combination of both the host and guest molecules. In the IR spectra of the complexes, the characteristic absorptions at 580 cm^{-1} of β -CD are broaden due to the splitting of the absorptions. Further research shows that the symmetry

of the host ring is decreased to a certain degree owing to the interaction between the host and guest molecules. The absorption bands at $1100\text{--}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are ascribed as the saturated C-H bending vibrations and the C-O stretching vibrations in the carboxylic groups. There is a strong peak round 2070 cm^{-1} , aroused by the C=O stretching vibration in the carboxylic group on the guest molecule.

In Fig. 4, in the area of $3400\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the absorption peaks of the complexes are strengthened and widened, showing that the hydrogen bonds between the host and guests are formed. The stretching vibrations of the O-H and N-H bonds on the guests are weakened, and the frequencies become less. Meanwhile, the absorption peaks are split thanks to the decrease of the symmetry, which is identical to the experiment²⁴.

There are two strong absorption peaks near 2000 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra of complexes 1 and 6 formed by the chiral enantiomers. One peak with relative lower frequency is attributed to the sulfhydryl group, and the other strong peak is arisen from the carbonyl group. There exist the two strong absorptions at 1975.9 and 2084.8 cm^{-1} in the

Fig. 4. The IR spectra of some complexes.

IR spectrum of complex 10. The frequency of the former one is lower, since the carbonyl stretching vibration in γ -C on the guest is decreased under the existence of the hydrogen bonds. The latter peak is generated owing to the C=O stretching vibration on the carboxyl group. The absorption peaks with medium intensity of complex 11 in the area of 2900–3100 cm^{-1} , representing the saturated C–H stretching vibrations, are analogous to those of the host in the same area. Since the glycine has the short carbon chain with the less steric effect, the hydrophobic interaction between the host and guest is small and the impact of this interaction on the C–H bonds is also tiny. Analogously, the O–H stretching vibration peaks on the host in the complexes are not clearly split. The N–H and O–H stretching vibration peaks on the guests are little changed. Guests 1 and 6 are the chiral enantiomers, so the IR spectra of their complexes are similar. Additionally, the peak of the group -SH in the IR spectrum of complex 1 formed by D-guest is red-shifted, while the first high-frequency peak and the peak of the aldehyde group are blue-shifted, relative to those of complex 6 formed by L-guest.

Guests 1 to 11 include the amino groups, so there are medium absorption peaks within the range of 3300–3500 cm^{-1} . The strongest absorption peaks of the host, guest 11 and complex 11 are 3426.8, 3425.8 and 3422.6 cm^{-1} , respectively. It is displayed that the -OH or -NH stretching vibrations are weakened and the frequencies are red-shifted due to the formation of the hydrogen bonds. The absorption peaks with the maximal frequency of the host, guest 11 and complex 11 are 3484.8, 3464.1 and 3487.8 cm^{-1} . It illustrates that the O–H and N–H stretching vibrations in complex 11 are intensified. The O–H bond on the carboxyl group on guest 11 in complex 11 is weakened due to the formation of the hydrogen bonding. Then the electron cloud density on atom O is enlarged owing to the partial proton delocalization, thus the N–H bond at the other end of guest 11 is strengthened and the vibration frequency becomes high.

Conclusion :

As stated above, β -CD can bind the non-essential amino acids to form the supramolecular complexes. The binding energies and some variables are impacted by the relative position between the host and the guest with the amino and carboxyl groups. The amino and carboxyl groups located near the small rim of the host can form the hydrogen-bonding meshwork with the host in order to stabilize the complex. β -CD also shows the chiral binding ability to the non-essential amino acids. There is a little

difference of the energy gaps between the complexes formed by the guests of the enantiomers. The energy gaps of the complexes are less than those of the host and guest molecules, owing to the effective overlapping of the electron cloud between the host and guests. It is anticipated that the first absorption peaks in the electronic spectra of the complexes should be red-shifted compared with that of the host. The formation of the hydrogen bonds between the host and guests leads to the decrease of the O–H and N–H stretching vibration frequencies. Meanwhile, the absorption peaks are split and the bands are broadened due to the decrease of the symmetry. The appearance of the IR spectra of the complexes formed by the chiral enantiomers looks similar.

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